

THE CRISIS AS A FACILITATOR OF INTRA- AND INTER- ORGANIZATIONAL COLLABORATION: THE CASE OF COVID 19

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Summary

The COVID-19 health crisis has shaken up the organization and operation of hospitals, a context that had already been under strain for several years, dealing with exhausted and sometimes even revolted healthcare professionals (Michot et al., 2019). Faced with the scale of the human challenge provoked by this crisis, the need to develop multi-professional teamwork to improve the efficiency of care and the agility of organizations has emerged as a major issue (Minvielle 2018 a, b). We pose the following research question: how has the health crisis fostered intra- and inter-organizational collaborations? In this paper, we will attempt to account for this relatively paradoxical situation by drawing on work carried out with professionals. In the first part, we show that the management science literature has produced useful resources for understanding the obstacles to collaborative work, notably based on the work of Carlile (2002, 2004) on the concepts of knowledge boundaries. We then present our methodology, based on several case studies. The results presented in the third section relate to the notions of boundary objects and boundary crossers. They are discussed in a final section devoted to the contributions of this research.

Keywords: COVID Crisis, Intra- And Inter-Organizational Collaborations, Public Hospital, Knowledge Frontiers, Frontier-Crosser, Frontier-Object.

INTRODUCTION

The need to develop multi-professional teamwork to improve the efficiency of care and the agility of organizations was established well before March 2020 (Minvielle 2018 a, b). It is still reiterated by the HAS (Référentiel 2020). However, during this time of crisis, the voice of facility managers has been little heard. However, the field of management science and management has remained very much in the background (Lorino and Mottis 2020). In this paper, we look back at this context of health crisis through the prism of management science, enabling us to understand the organizational conditions established within hospitals. During this period, it seemed that all obstacles to intra- and inter-organizational collaboration and proximity management had disappeared (Dumez and Minvielle 2021 and 2022; Grimaldi and Vernant 2022; Nobre 2021). The research presented here aims to identify the factors that have made it possible to overcome these obstacles.

We pose the following research question: **how has the health crisis fostered intra- and inter-organizational collaborations?** We seek to understand how the COVID crisis became a facilitator of intra- and inter-organizational collaborations.

In the first part, we show that the literature in management science has produced useful resources for understanding the obstacles to collaborative work, based in particular on Carlile's (2002, 2004) reading of the concepts of knowledge boundaries, boundary-objects and boundary-crossers. We then present our methodology, based on several case studies. The third part will be devoted to the presentation of the results, leading to a final discussion of the contributions of this research.

1. OBSTACLES TO COLLABORATIVE WORK. A MANAGEMENT SCIENCE APPROACH

Multi-actor collaboration is complex (Morin, 1990). It brings together a diversity of players with different professions, backgrounds, disciplines and organizations. This diversity is a source of distance, divergent stakes and interests, dissonance and tension, all of which are reflected in the notion of "knowledge frontiers". Carlile (2002, 2004) offers an interesting reading of knowledge boundaries, which he classifies into three categories: syntactic, semantic and pragmatic. These three levels of boundary are related to the properties of knowledge that are localized, embedded and invested (Carlile, 2002, 2004; Edmondson & Harvey, 2018). The first "syntactic" boundary level is located in terminology. Syntactic boundaries manifest themselves as differences in the way language is used that can hinder communication and cross-comprehension. As for the "semantic" boundary, it refers to the construction of meaning that has to be carried out when the co-presenting stakeholders are no longer settled into a routine but have to deal with knowledge that is new to them. Interpretations are so automatic that people may be unaware of these differences. Different interpreting systems create translation challenges. Finally, the "pragmatic" frontier refers to the different interests of the stakeholders involved in a collective activity. People have their own rationalities, and place more or less value on specific principles and ways of doing things. Depending on the type of organization or function, individuals will tend to pursue certain interests more than others (Carlile, 2002).

The boundary-crossing process is based on the dialogue that each participant engages with the perspectives of the other participants in sufficient depth to facilitate the combination, expansion and evolution of knowledge (Tsoukas, 2009; Edmondson & Harvey, 2018). Through reciprocal interactions within the team, each member participates in the production or transformation of knowledge. At the same time, boundaries are interfaces that are sources of productive interaction, knowledge and experience sharing, and thus of reciprocal learning (Akkerman & Bakker, 2018). The dynamics differ depending on whether the boundaries are particularly thick or relatively thin, in which case a limited degree of interaction may suffice (Edmondson & Harvey, 2018). Crossing knowledge boundaries within a given organization, or between organizations, is an increasingly common innovation strategy that relies on diversity of knowledge and variety of views and ideas, but can be difficult to put into practice, so that innovation is not always realized (Edmondson & Harvey, 2018). Crossing borders presents several challenges. As they cross boundaries, team

members have the opportunity to examine their own perceptions from a new angle and reflect on the project or the way they do their job (Edmondson & Harvey, 2018).

There are, however, a number of difficulties that complicate the task of crossing boundaries. Based on observations of different professional communities working together, Bechky (2003) finds that difficulties in sharing community knowledge are rooted in differences of language and practice. According to Tushman & Scanlan (1981), crossing boundaries is a two-stage process: just as someone learning a new language has to learn both vocabulary and how to interpret contextual messages, i.e. non-verbal signs, voice intonations and use of space, so communication across organizational boundaries requires learning local codes, patterns, languages and specific conceptual frameworks.

To facilitate collaboration within an organization or at a territorial level, the notions of boundary objects and boundary brokers are an interesting avenue. Practices involving dialogues (stories and metaphors), objects (diagrams, drawings, plans, prototypes, models) or even people (intermediaries, translators, knowledge brokers) have been described in the literature to help actors and teams cross knowledge boundaries in order to face complex problems and find approaches to solving them (Bechky, 2003; Hargadon, 2003; Obstfeld, 2005). According to Koskinen (2005), boundary objects can be abstract or concrete, and interpreted differently by different organizations. It is the discussion of these differences that makes a shared understanding possible. They thus encourage interaction and create contextualized knowledge and understanding between multiple stakeholders (Koskinen, 2005). Akkerman & Bakker (2011) highlight several learning mechanisms facilitated by border processes and objects: identification (individuals and groups become aware of the differences and links between their practices and those of others); coordination (they learn how to work together at borders by developing sustainable practices and routines); reflexivity (they extend their perspectives and practices by working at borders) and transformation (which involves collaboration, co-development of practices, routines and knowledge). Obstfeld (2005) examines the micro-processes in the social networks of border-crossers involved in organizational innovation, and how they introduce disconnected people or facilitate new coordination between connected people. This "Tertius iungens" (or "linking third party") contrasts with the "Tertius Gaudens" of structural hole theory, which turns people against each other for their own interests. Innovation would be facilitated by dense social networks, knowledge diversity and social skills. According to Tushman & Scanlan (1981), internal and external relationships are necessary but not sufficient conditions for crossing boundaries. In addition, individuals need to be well connected to external and internal information zones, and able to disseminate new information and ideas to their more locally-oriented colleagues. According to the authors, only people who understand boundaries can effectively cross them and play the role of intermediary or translator. This notion of an intermediary role echoes a managerial dimension and, more specifically, the proximity management often lacking in hospitals and healthcare establishments. During the health crisis, the boundaries of knowledge seem to have been more permeable, favoring teamwork. We will attempt to verify this and identify the conditions that favored it, based on several case studies.

2. CASE STUDIES ON WORKING IN MULTI-SKILLED TEAMS

Collaboration and cooperation are not easy things; they seem to depend on several parameters that we will try to highlight through several cases (Flyvbjerg, 2006, Stake, 2005, Yin, 2014) studied with a pragmatist approach (Lorino, 2020): the implementation of a surgical robot in a urology operating room some twenty years ago, and the difficulty of acquiring new technologies today within the same operating room; the development of a convergence portal enabling Nancy University Hospital to work with the ICL (Institut de Cancérologie de Lorraine), which was accelerated thanks to the health crisis, but whose retention may still be questioned over time; experimentation with the "forfait au parcours" system; collaboration between the chu and EPHADs, notably in terms of training in infectious risk, which has been extended beyond the radiation protection department; the regulation of intensive care beds and operation chardon 3, facilitated by the white plan preparation exercise; internal structural reorganizations and the decision-making process set up in the context of a health crisis at a hospital in Luxembourg.

We conducted at least three research interviews with each person involved in the multi-stakeholder collaborations studied. Each interview lasted an average of an hour and a half. The interviews were recorded and partly transcribed. They enabled us to detail the practices and processes involved in intra- and inter-organizational collaborations.

3. MAIN RESULTS

The latent crisis was more of an obstacle to technology development and multi-stakeholder collaboration, while the COVID-19 crisis was a facilitating factor for intra- and inter-organizational collaborations. We present here the results for each case study.

3.1 The development of a convergence portal enabling Nancy University Hospital to work with the Institut de Cancérologie de Lorraine)

The COVID crisis has led to a number of surgical reschedulings, including in urology. The former and new heads of the urology department at the Institut de Cancérologie de Lorraine (ICL) have decided to maintain patient consultations at Nancy University Hospital. A partnership has been set up between the CHU and the ICL to provide surgery for patients requiring urgent treatment. To ensure that patients from the CHU could be operated on at the ICL, patient information had to be shared between the two establishments. The convergence portal was quickly developed. This is an interface for sharing information on patients to be operated on between the CHU and the ICL. This portal had been an existing project for many years. The COVID crisis accelerated the development of the portal, given the urgency of the situation. The development of the convergence portal was accelerated thanks to the health crisis, but its preservation may still be questioned over time.

The portal acts as a border object between the two establishments: CHU and ICL. The head of the urology department at the CHU appears to be a border-crosser, since he already operates regularly at the ICL.

3.2 Collaboration between CHU and EPHAD: training in infectious risk management

In the residential facility for dependent elderly people studied (EHPAD), a platform with the various local players took shape during the COVID-19 crisis.

Infectious risk management is the responsibility of the Nancy University Hospital's Patient-User Territorial Department. At the start of the COVID crisis, the head of this department forged links with EHPADs to offer risk management training, which was extended beyond the radiation protection department. This training acts as a "border object" between the CHU and the EHPADs. Similarly, given her background, which began as a nurse, the head of the department will play the role of border-crosser.

3.3 Internal structural reorganization and decision-making in a Luxembourg hospital establishment

The case study presented here was carried out in a Luxembourg hospital following the first wave of the health crisis in September 2020. Several interviews were conducted with nursing and medical professionals, as well as members of management. Two major events were reported by interviewees.

In the first case, the care manager and an anesthetist practicing in the intensive care unit receiving Covid patients.

The first concerns the internal structural reorganization of the intensive care unit. The care of patients hospitalized in this department involves a number of players whose cooperation is not always obvious:

"It's not always easy to work together, as we each have our own priorities" (Nursing manager, intensive care unit).

The arrival of Covid patients has radically changed the organization of the department, which has been split into two parts to offer two distinct circuits dedicated respectively to Covid patients and non-Covid patients. This new organization was built by all the professionals involved.

"We thought together and made decisions together. We combined our skills to come up with the best organization" (nursing executive, intensive care unit);

"We talked a lot together, asked each other what you thought, and above all, we made up our minds quickly" (anesthesiologist).

Gradually, teamwork was established, combining the skills of doctors, nurses and logisticians, and supporting cooperation around service organization. Covid patient care procedures became boundary objects, enabling status boundaries to be crossed through shared representations. Everyone's role has been identified, based on recognition of each person's skills.

At facility level, the case study also highlights the upheaval in the decision-making process. Decisions are taken within the crisis unit, made up of representatives of different professional categories: general manager, director of care, administrative director, medical director,

resuscitation doctor, etc. Each person presents the information available to them from the field. Each member presents the information they have at their disposal from the field. Regular meetings to take stock of the situation, based on figures from the field provided by each member of the team, have led to consensus-based decisions on the course of action to be taken and the necessary adjustments to be made.

Discussions also covered the conditions under which the virus is transmitted, as well as state-of-the-art treatment methods:

"We learned together, we shared our information to decide together" (anesthesiologist).

Information sharing and transparency around a common language facilitated cooperation.

A mechanism for creating and disseminating knowledge has been set up within the crisis unit, creating a space for exchange that has become a frontier object. The members of the crisis unit have become border crossers, gathering and reporting information from the field and disseminating the decisions taken to the players in the field.

3.4 Summary Of Results

The results presented concur on the presence of border objects (platforms, portals, etc.) and border-crossers enabling border crossings.

Another finding is that multi-party collaborations are the result of many little things that are difficult to predict: interpersonal relationships that work well, chance encounters, organizational dysfunctions that generate a need for cooperation and collaboration.

DISCUSSION

In hospitals, for doctors, paramedical staff and technicians, management is often associated with a set of bureaucratic constraints, financial requirements dictated by the quest for performance and even often paradoxical injunctions born of the "New Public Management" (NPM) put forward and criticized by Bellini & al. (2018). This latent organizational crisis (Claris, 2020; Blanchard & Tirol, 2021) seems to have been exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic (Bergeron *et al.*, 2020) and, at the same time, the health crisis linked to the pandemic caused by the COVID-19 virus, had the effect of giving hospital staff a breath of fresh air, a kind of salvific and comforting "Open Bar" parenthesis despite the increased demands and overtime! The crisis brings both risks and opportunities. Indeed, according to François Jullien, the word "crisis" is spelled "Wei-ji" in the Chinese language in use, and covers both danger and opportunity. "Danger comes to be reversed into its opposite" (Jullien, 2020). Despite the lack of hindsight, we can say that the COVID-19 crisis was not explosive, and the healthcare system held up well overall (Dumez & Minvielle, 2020). The hospital experimented with an agile organization: crisis cells, informal meetings, exchanges of information on WhatsApp, and exceptional and substantial funding. More precisely, the hospital has experimented with a more agile mode of organization, even if it is still difficult to reconcile structure and agility (Nobre, 2020, p. 453). However, the road is not completely clear,

as evoked by Antonio Machado's poem: "Traveller there is not a pas de chemin, le chemin se fait en marchant": "... Voyageur, le chemin C'est les traces de tes pas / C'est tout; voyageur, il n'y a pas de chemin, /Le chemin se fait en marchant / Le chemin se fait en marchant / Et quand tu regardes en arrière / Tu vois le sentier que jamais / Tu ne dois à battre à nouveau Voyageur! There are no paths / Nothing but wakes on the sea. Everything passes and everything remains / But our business is to pass / To pass by tracing / Paths Paths on the sea".

The crisis has encouraged inter-professional cooperation, facilitating the crossing of knowledge boundaries. This was made possible by a collective process of knowledge creation based on the state of the art and scientific recommendations relating to the virus, its transmission and effective therapeutic management, followed by dissemination of this knowledge. This knowledge, continually adjusted in line with scientific advances, has enabled us to adapt the organization of care, professional practices and so on. The semantic, syntactic and pragmatic boundaries thus became permeable, with the introduction of tools, exchange forums, methods, etc., bringing players together and leading them to adopt a common language, a source of shared meaning and enabling shared practices. Exchanges were built around border objects, enabling interactions and a shared understanding of the situation, based on recognition of each person's skills, contributing to the construction of a multi-professional team. Individual interests fade into the background in favor of a common interest: the collective fight against a pandemic. Differences in language and practice have disappeared.

However, border objects are not always enough to cross borders. Intermediate managers play a decisive role in this process. They are able to transmit and translate knowledge. It is important to note, however, the importance of leadership on the part of this intermediary player, who is capable of inspiring the confidence of his colleagues. Knowledge is heard and integrated, generating the application of recommended practices. Teamwork, whether intra- or inter-institutional, cannot be decreed. In particular, it presupposes a specific form of leadership and the existence of formal and informal discussion forums that enable everyone to be recognized for their contribution to the department's collective activity, without obscuring power relations and the tensions they generate (Bergeron, 2020). However, as Olivier Claris' report (2020) points out, the departments have not found their means of expression within the divisions, even though they are the level of reference for a large proportion of hospital staff and patients alike.

CONCLUSION

The latent crisis that has prevailed in hospitals for many years has not made it easy to bring intra- and inter-institutional collaboration projects to fruition. On the other hand, the COVID crisis seems to have facilitated the successful completion of certain projects (e.g., the COVID portal. convergence, for example) that can be seen as border objects between different communities or organizations. In each case studied, a border-crosser facilitated the crossing of knowledge borders. To ensure the continuity of this collaboration, we need to think about the creation of border objects, such as patients and border-crossers.

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